

Reaction to BPH biotype 2 of wild rice lines originating from *Oryza officinalis*.^a IRRRI, 1989.

Variety	Damage rating ^b
IR54742-1-11-17-12-3	1
IR54742-1-11-17-26-2	1
IR54742-1-11-17-26-3	1
IR54742-1-17-12-26-2	1
IR54742-1-17-20-8-1	3
IR54742-1-17-20-8-3	1
IR54742-1-18-12-11-1	1
IR54742-1-18-12-11-2	1
IR54742-1-18-12-11-3	1
IR54742-5-36-4-17-1	3
IR54742-5-36-4-17-3	3
IR54742-6-20-3-9-2	1
IR54742-6-20-3-9-3	1
IR54742-6-20-3-22-2	1
IR54742-6-20-3-22-3	3
IR54742-11-1-9-15-2	1
IR54742-11-2-8-2-1	3
IR54742-11-2-8-2-3	3
IR54742-11-17-10-5-2	3
IR54742-18-17-20-15-3	3
IR54742-22-14-24-22-2	3
IR54742-22-19-3-7-3	3
IR54742-22-19-3-15-1	3
IR54742-23-11-19-6-1	1
IR54742-23-11-19-6-3	1
IR54742-23-19-16-12-1	3
IR54742-23-19-16-12-2	1
IR54742-23-19-16-12-3	1
IR54742-31-9-26-15-2	3
IR54742-31-21-20-10-2	3
IR54742-33-18-20-3-2	3
IR54742-33-18-20-3-3	1
IR54742-38-13-15-2-2	3
IR54742-38-26-10-17-1	1
IR54742-41-15-30-23-1	1
IR54742-41-15-30-23-2	1
IR54742-41-15-30-23-3	1
IR54742-41-40-20-19-1	3
IR54742-4140-20-19-2	3
IR54745-2-2-25-26-1	1
IR54745-2-2-25-26-3	1
IR.54745-2-10-17-8-2	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-1	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-2	3
IR54745-2-21-12-17-4	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-5	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-6	1
IR54745-2-23-19-8-1	1
IR54745-2-23-19-8-2	3
IR54745-2-23-19-8-3	1
IR.54745-2-28-22-7-2	1
IR54745-2-37-5-26-1	1
IR54745-2-37-5-26-2	1
IR54745-2-37-5-26-3	1
IR54745-2-45-3-24-2	1
IR54748-1-17-12-1	1
IR54748-1-17-12-3	1
IR54748-1-17-25-3	1
IR54742-9-44	3
IR54742-9-4-5	1
IR54742-19-2-3	1
IR74 (resistant check)	1
TN1 (susceptible check)	9

^a Av of 3 replications. All entries, except TN1 showed resistance. ^b By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Leaffolder (LF) damage and yield loss on some selected rice varieties

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We studied the effect of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Gueneé infestation on panicle length and weight during 1987 wet season.

Kranti, Madhuri, Mahsuri, Asha, Gurmatia, Safri 17, Makdo, and CR1014 were transplanted in 5- × 4.60-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. The crop was fertilized at 40-30-20 kg NPK/ha.

After flag leaf emergence, 15 hills

of each variety were selected at random. Infested and healthy leaves were counted. Panicle length and panicle weight were measured at harvest.

The data suggested that all the varieties were susceptible to LF (see table). The degree of susceptibility was in order Kranti > Mahsuri > Madhuri > Asha > Gurmatia > Safri 17 > Makdo > CR1014.

Correlations indicated that the higher the infestation, the shorter the panicle length and the lighter the panicle weight. But correlation coefficients were significant only between leaf damage and panicle weight in Gurmatia and Safri 17 and only between leaf damage and panicle length in CR1014, Kranti, and Madhuri. □

LF damage and yield of selected rice varieties. Madhya Pradesh, India, 1987 wet season.

Variety	Leaf damage (%)	Panicle wt (g)		Panicle length (cm)		Correlation ^a	
		Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Damage-panicle wt	Damage-panicle length
CR1014	12.21	2.00-2.56	2.17	16.01-19.01	17.07	-0.30	-0.78*
Kranti	24.63	1.52-2.30	1.87	17.01-20.09	18.08	-0.18	-0.63*
Mahsuri	24.32	2.59-2.79	2.26	15.08-17.04	16.05	-0.45	-0.47
Gurmatia	15.96	1.43-1.83	1.64	17.06-21.01	17.09	-0.98*	-0.19
Safri 17	15.13	0.86-1.01	0.94	16.03-17.03	16.08	-0.68*	-0.27
Madhuri	23.46	1.73-1.96	1.81	17.06-22.05	20.09	-0.23	-0.52*
Asha	16.52	1.68-2.14	1.87	16.01-20.05	19.07	-0.41	-0.48
Makdo	13.39	1.96-2.30	2.22	15.03-18.03	16.04	-0.39	-0.14

^a* = significant at the 0.05 level.

Adverse soils tolerance

Performance of selected rice genotypes in alkaline, saline, and normal soils and their interaction with climate factors

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Soil salinity and alkalinity associated with low temperature are the major problems of the coastal area of the Salado River basin, Buenos Aires Province.

We evaluated 81 cultivars and 9 local lines and varieties for alkalinity and salinity tolerance, under temperate climate conditions (35° south latitude).

The severely deteriorated alkali soil (Typic Natraqualf) of the Salado River basin is characterized by high pH (9.6), sodicity (exchangeable sodium percentage exceeding 60), calcium carbonate precipitation, clay texture. Soil salinity was created artificially by adding NaCl to 8 dS/m at seeding. Normal soil was a Typic Argiudoll with excellent agronomic characteristics.

Entries were dry seeded in problem soils 1 and 2 Oct 1987 and in

Agronomic data for test entries. La Plata, Argentina, 1987.^a

Designation	Alkaline							Saline							Normal						
	Scores			Germination (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)	Scores			Germination (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)	Scores			Germination (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)
	VP	RP	PA					VP	RP	PA					VP	RP	PA				
Gz1368-5-2	6	4	5	15	59	17	175	6	5	5	30	67	19	—	6	3	5	20	79	19	165
Gz1368-5-54	6	4	5	5	62	17	168	6	4	4	20	65	17	166	6	3	5	20	82	21	165
IR10154-117-2-3-3-3	6	5	6	10	47	16	152	5	4	6	35	54	18	173	6	3	5	30	71	18	178
IR10206-29-2-1	6	6	6	5	57	18	—	5	4	4	20	72	29	—	5	2	4	30	84	21	168
IR19392-33-3	6	7	6	10	42	15	178	6	5	7	10	—	—	—	6	4	5	10	72	18	164
IR19743-25-2-2-3-1	5	5	5	35	51	16	148	5	4	5	10	60	18	162	6	4	5	5	70	17	174
IR28	6	5	4	35	56	18	152	5	3	5	30	62	18	151	6	4	5	10	90	21	161
IR31375-3-3-3	5	4	5	15	72	20	178	4	3	8	20	—	—	169	7	2	6	30	92	21	—
IR32307-107-3-2-2	4	4	4	50	56	22	173	4	3	7	20	—	—	165	6	3	6	30	78	21	—
IR32429-47-3-2-2	4	4	4	40	60	17	154	3	3	6	25	—	—	147	6	4	5	20	65	20	174
IR37379-20-1-2-1-1	5	5	7	55	45	16	141	5	4	7	20	50	16	131	6	2	5	40	56	14	169
IR8238-B-B-57-2-1	5	5	5	30	73	19	174	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	6	2	6	40	87	22	—
KS-282	4	4	4	50	61	19	172	5	5	7	20	—	—	—	6	2	5	30	80	21	178
IR9129-209-2-2-2-3	6	5	6	55	53	18	163	5	4	6	50	64	19	160	6	3	5	30	72	20	174
<i>Local checks</i>																					
Itape P.A.	4	4	5	40			153	5	2	3	50			164							
Yerua P.A.	5	3	5	35			153	4	2	3	30			153							
H198-1-3-2-3-1	3	2	4	60			165	3	2	3	15			134							
H198-8-1-2-1	4	2	4	10			161	3	2	3	15			160							
H238-5-1	3	2	3	30			164	3	2	3	10			146							
H238-20-1-1	4	2	4	25			162	3	2	3	20			138							
H238-47-1	was not seeded							3	2	3	20			152							
H238-82-2-1	3	2	3	30			169	was not seeded													
H175	4	2	3	45			159	was not seeded													

^a VP = vegetative phase, RP = reproductive phase, PA = phenotypic acceptability.

normal soil 20 Oct, at 1 row/entry and 25-cm spacing. Germination began 17 Oct, the test plot was irrigated 15 d later. Agronomic data were collected each 15 d and subsumed into values for vegetative phase, reproductive phase, and phenotypic acceptability (see table).

All exotic lines were affected adversely, mainly by temperature and photoperiod. Climate-adapted local checks showed the best performance under both treatments.

Entries showed more tolerance in the reproductive than in the vegetative

phase. More plants died during the vegetative phase.

Plant height and panicle length correlated strongly with soil problems and were more affected by alkalinity than by salinity. □

Extragenic basis of salt tolerance in rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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NIAB Rice-1 has been found to be relatively salt tolerant and Basmati 370 to be relatively salt sensitive. To clarify the extragenic basis of salt tolerance, we made reciprocal crosses between the two genotypes. The F₁ hybrids and the parents were transplanted at 45 d after seeding on nonsaline and saline sodic field basins. Salinization of the field basins was accomplished using four commercial salts of MgCl, NaCl,

CaCl₂, and Na₂SO₄ in a 1:4:5:10 equivalent ratio.

The experiment was laid out in a complete randomized block design

with three replications. Interrow and intrarow spacing was 20 cm. Data for yield and yield components were recorded on 10 plants/replication.

Inheritance of yield and yield components under normal and saline sodic soils.^a Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Parent or F ₁ combination	Nonsaline soil ^b				Saline soil ^c			
	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Yield (g/plant)	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Yield (g/plant)
Basmati 370	139.8 b	13.8 b	36.7 d	13.5 c	126.8 b	9.0 c	25.0 c	9.0 c
Basmati 370/NIAB Rice-1	162.8 a	21.6 a	39.7 b	17.0 b	143.9 a	18.0 a	34.8 b	14.0 b
NIAB Rice-1/Basmati 370	159.2 a	20.4 a	42.9 b	18.4 ab	144.9 a	19.0 a	34.1 b	12.9 b
NIAB Rice-1	143.8 b	19.0 a	59.0 a	20.4 a	122.7 b	15.6 b	51.4 a	17.1 a

^aIn a column, values followed by identical letters are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bpH 7.6, EC 3.0 dS/m, SAR 9.0. ^cpH 8.7, EC 6.2 dS/m, SAR 20.0.